

Effective amount of N fertilizer for direct seeding on wet surface of reclaimed saline soil in Korea

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The demand for changing cultural methods from machine transplanting to direct seeding is a current trend in Korea. We identified the appropriate amount of N fertilizer for direct seeding on a wet surface of reclaimed saline soil in Korea.

The experiment was conducted at the Gyehwa substation of the Honam National Agricultural Experiment Station during 1996-97 using a randomized complete block design with three replications on saline soil that contained 0.2-0.4% NaCl in soil solution. Four N levels were tested with a control of 210 kg N ha⁻¹ as standard fertilization for machine transplanting. The results showed that seedling establishment increased slightly up to 180 kg N ha⁻¹ but decreased at 210 kg N ha⁻¹ in direct seeding. Culm length is higher in direct seeding with 210 kg N ha⁻¹. Field lodging in the maturing stage is more serious in direct seeding than in transplanting, as noted by the score of 5 out of 9 under visual assessment (Table 1).

Panicle number and spikelet number per unit area increased significantly at above 180 kg N ha⁻¹ compared with machine transplanting at 210 kg N ha⁻¹ as a control. The percentage of ripened grains and 1,000-grain weight were higher for machine transplanting than direct seeding at the same amount of N. Milled rice yield showed no significant differences between direct seeding and machine transplanting at the same amount of N (Table 2). As a result, we found that the appropriate N level for direct seeding in reclaimed saline soil was 180 kg ha⁻¹. This amount will best prevent field lodging and save on fertilizer and labor costs. ■

Table 1. General characteristics of rice as influenced by N fertilizer under wet seeding in reclaimed saline soil, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Cultural method	N amount (kg ha ⁻¹)	Seedling establishment (no. m ⁻²)	Heading date	Culm length (cm)	Field lodging ^a
Direct seeding	100	100	12 Aug	79	0
	150	110	12 Aug	81	1
	180	115	13 Aug	83	3
	210	99	14 Aug	84	5
Machine transplanting (standard)	210	—	16 Aug	80	3

^aOn a scale of 0-9, where 0 = none, 1 = low, and 9 = high.

Table 2. Yield components and yield according to amount of N fertilizer under wet seeding in reclaimed saline soil, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97^a.

Cultural method	N amount (kg ha ⁻¹)	Panicles (no. m ⁻²)	Spikelets (no. m ⁻²) × 10 ³	Ripened grain (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Milled rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield index
Direct seeding	120	375 b	26.6 c	85.1 b	24.6 a	4.6 b	91
	150	381 b	28.8 b	85.3 b	24.5 a	4.7 b	93
	180	397 a	30.9 a	84.1 bc	24.9 a	4.8 a	96
	210	401 a	31.9 a	83.2 c	23.8 b	4.7 ab	94
Machine transplanting (standard)	210	346 c	27.2 bc	89.7 a	25.3 a	5.1 a	100

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Identifying optimum seeding time for direct seeding on a wet field surface in reclaimed saline soil in Korea

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Rice cultivation in Korea is changing from machine transplanting to direct seeding to save on labor costs and to increase profits. We therefore identified the appropriate seeding time for direct seeding on a wet field surface in

reclaimed saline soil in the southern part of Korea.

The experiment was conducted at the Gyehwa substation of the Honam National Agricultural Experiment Station during 1996-97 using a split-plot design with three replications in a saline soil that contained 0.2-0.4% NaCl in soil solution. Three varieties were used to represent each maturing type: Shinunbongbyeo (early maturing), Gancheokbyeo (mid-maturing), and Gyehwabyeo (late maturing). The results showed that for Shinunbong-

Table 1. Seedling establishment (no. m²) according to seeding times on a wet field surface in reclaimed saline soil^a, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Seeding time	Shinunbongbyeo	Gancheokbyeo	Gyehwabyeo
10 May	103 a	104 a	108 a
20 May	97 a	109 a	107 a
30 May	92 a	98 a	93 a
10 Jun	89 a	79 b	76 b

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

byeo, seeding time had no effect on seeding establishment and for Gancheokbyeo and Gyehwabyeo, seeding establishment adversely affected them if they were seeded after June (Table 1).

Panicle number per unit area for Shinunbongbyeo was not significantly different for seeding time; for Gancheokbyeo and Gyehwabyeo, panicle number per unit area decreased if they were seeded after 10 Jun. For 1,000-grain weight, seeding time had no effect on all three varieties.

Spikelet number per unit area and percentage of ripened grains were reduced significantly when the seeding time was 10 Jun for all maturing types. Milled rice yield for Shinunbongbyeo was not affected by seeding time. For Gancheokbyeo and Gyehwabyeo, milling yield was reduced significantly

Table 2. Yield components and yield according to seeding times on wet field surface in reclaimed saline soil^a, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Cultivar	Seeding time	Panicles (no. m ²)	Spikelets (no. m ²) × 10 ⁴	Ripened grain (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Milled rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Shinunbongbyeo	10 May	417 a	30.7 a	89 a	21.7 a	4.5 a
	20 May	414 a	30.6 a	89 a	21.4 a	4.4 a
	30 May	406 a	28.3 ab	87 ab	21.5 a	4.3 a
Gancheokbyeo	10 Jun	399 a	27.2 b	86 b	21.3 a	4.1 a
	10 May	411 a	31.6 a	90 a	22.7 a	4.5 a
	20 May	405 a	32.9 a	92 a	23.0 a	4.6 a
Gyehwabyeo	30 May	397 a	31.5 a	92 a	23.1 a	4.6 a
	10 Jun	361 b	25.3 b	86 b	22.2 a	3.8 b
	10 May	421 a	29.3 a	90 a	24.0 a	4.5 a
	20 May	412 a	31.0 a	90 a	24.3 a	4.8 a
	30 May	398 a	28.4 ab	87 b	23.9 a	4.4 b
	10 Jun	355 b	24.4 b	84 c	23.1 a	3.4 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

when the seeding time was late May and later (Table 2). The results indicated that the best seeding time for early-maturing types was from May to early

June. The most appropriate seeding time for mid- and late-maturing varieties was the middle of May. ■

Stress tolerance — excess water

Distinguishing seedling traits in deepwater rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Deepwater rice genotypes are characterized by their elongation ability under excess water. This character is expressed approximately 4-6 wk after seeding. However, young germinating seedlings within 7-15 d after seeding can be identified for elongation ability from morphological characters such as mesocotyl elongation and length of the second leaf blade, which can be used to distinguish deepwater types from their nondeepwater counterparts.

A comparative assessment was made for these two parameters taking 10 genotypes from both deepwater and nondeepwater rice during the dry and wet seasons, 1996, at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. Seeding was done at three depths—4, 6, and 8 cm—under normal pot culture as well as under dark with seeds germinated in petri dishes. Observations were recorded for mesocotyl elongation and length of the second leaf blade on 1-wk-

Length of mesocotyl and second leaf blade of deepwater and nondeepwater rice varieties (data pooled over two seasons).

Variety	Mesocotyl length (mm)			Germination in dark	Length of second leaf blade (mm)
	Seeding depth				
	4 cm	6 cm	8 cm		
Deepwater rice					
Jalamagna	26.15	37.10	53.40	3.75	37.40
TCA4	28.75	42.40	63.35	5.20	38.25
Jalanidhi	25.95	31.65	38.05	2.15	49.10
NDGR410	27.25	44.40	63.75	3.08	49.35
NDGR413	28.00	34.50	43.75	1.75	47.80
LPR85	27.05	36.75	50.80	2.25	47.10
TCA12	28.45	33.90	43.55	1.35	49.90
Chakia 59	26.55	38.00	43.25	1.60	48.10
Madhukar	26.55	34.50	46.05	1.87	48.15
Jalapriya	32.40	39.55	47.20	2.25	45.45
Mean	27.71	37.28	49.32	2.33	46.06
Nondeepwater rice					
Khao Y Khao	17.25	26.25	29.55	0.38	59.15
IET7590	21.85	28.15	36.15	0.40	59.90
Kwan-Fu-1	21.10	20.75	27.20	0.23	63.50
Mtu-6	22.10	28.75	38.35	0.58	56.45
TK Deep straw 34-774	17.55	26.20	27.40	0.10	50.60
Deep straw 24-500	12.40	19.35	21.20	0.05	58.95
Samson Polo (YS386)	21.45	25.05	37.85	0.55	54.25
Daeng Laem	17.85	18.85	22.90	0.45	62.65
Basmati 802	19.25	21.35	24.05	0.43	57.10
Savitri	13.25	15.80	19.90	0.28	51.00
Mean	18.41	23.05	28.46	0.34	57.36

old seedlings by taking a sample of 10 seedlings from each type.

The two seasons were found to be homogeneous, with nonsignificant differences for the two characters as tested

by Bartlett's test. The pooled data over two seasons (see table) indicated higher mesocotyl elongation for deepwater rice than for nondeepwater rice varieties for both pot culture and dark petri